

Digitizing the Margins: The Making of Peripheral Heritage

Gowtham Rajan M R
M.A History., D.T.T.M., NET., SET.
Independent Researcher
ORCID: 0009-0001-6983-800X
gowthamrajamr@gmail.com

Abstract

Heritage is often linked with larger entities such as palaces, forts, large temples and landscapes, while ignoring the minute and mundane entities encountered in daily life. Heritage is typically associated with the core or dominant presence, while the periphery or fringe is ignored. This paper argues against this attitude and suggests that the traditions and cultures of mundane and peripheral entities are equally worthy of consideration. To achieve this preservation of such entities is essential so that they can survive for more deeper study in the future. Digital technologies would be useful in carrying out this task. To support this hypothesis, texts and locations from the margins of historical knowledge are examined, and two ways of using digital technologies to preserve them are suggested in the paper.

Keywords

- Peripheral heritage
- Digital Preservation
- Cultural Documentation

Introduction

Heritage is generally defined as traditions, qualities and culture, which we inherit from the past, live in the present, and would pass on to the future. And for any society, preserving and transmitting its heritage is considered as a major responsibility. With this consciousness, many fruitful initiatives were, and are, taken by many societies, including the Tamil Society, which resulted in the proliferation of knowledge on a society's heritage. But on viewing it from an ethical angle, an important question arises: Whether every people's, area's, and entity's heritage is preserved and passed on to the future generation? There is no affirmative answer to this question because societies tend to focus largely on protecting and imparting the heritage of the dominant/core/prevalent, and the heritage of the periphery/fringe/isolated is largely ignored.

In this circumstance, it is very crucial to preserve and impart the heritage of the hitherto ignored people/area/entity. For this task, modern digital technologies would be helpful.

This paper stresses that by using digital technologies, the traditions and cultures of the periphery can be documented, which would produce new knowledge and add more dimensions to the hitherto known understanding of heritage. Most importantly such documentation would help prevent the disappearance of fragile traditions and cultures.

Since the term heritage comprises a wide period within its ambit, it is difficult to make remarks on the entire past of a society. Therefore, the scope of this paper is restricted to the heritage that emerged out of the 19th and 20th centuries CE. The reason for choosing such a recent past is to stress the fact the traditions and cultures of the margins are largely ignored even when the subject matter being discussed is relatively recent and has ample sources. It is only due to a lack of initiative that these sources begin to fade away without imparting the knowledge they hold into the pages of history and thereby never mature into becoming a heritage of the society.

Digital Mediation and the Making of Heritage

With the advent of sub-altern studies in history,¹ new ways of looking at the past began to emerge. The most crucial point raised by the school was that the existing narratives tended to ignore the lives of those in the periphery and focus solely on the core.² Similarly, when it comes to heritage, the core dominates.

To change this, it is necessary to transmit the traditions and cultures of those in the periphery as heritage, and the first step in this process lies in preserving such entities. Modern digital technologies play a major role in facilitating this preservation. As Milan Kundera exclaimed, 'The Struggle of man against power is the struggle of memory against forgetting'³ and in this sense, preservation becomes an act of resistance against erasure.

Two ways in which modern technologies can be used to preserve the heritage of the periphery, and the knowledge that can be gained from such preservation, are as follows:

Digitizing texts is one such method – many small works that document the traditions, practices, habits, and rituals of the periphery exist in society, but they are fragile, both materially and ideationally, due to their rarity and continued neglect in collective memory and historical documentation. Digitizing and hosting these works on a digital platform can significantly extend their life and accessibility, and would result in passing those as heritage to the future generations.

To give an example, '*Gujili Ilakkiyam*', a form of populist Tamil literature prevalent in the late 19th and early 20th centuries CE,⁴ was a medium where the current happenings and other popular things in society were recorded and discussed among the ordinary masses, and that too in language of the commoners, often recited as songs. For example, a Gujili song named '*Mel Parakum Motorcar Sindhu*', written by Munusamy Mudaliar in 1913, admires the beauty of a flying vehicle, which the author perceives as a car.⁵ And another Gujili song named, '*Vilakkuennaikum Krishna oil Enginra Mannanenaikum Sandaiyin Kummi - Nallaennai Samadhana Paduthuthal*' written by one Thirupuliyur Ethirajulu Naidu, printed and sold at Tiruchirappalli,⁶ metaphorically narrates a clash between groundnut oil and kerosene, which was mediated by gingelly oil. One of the interesting things to note, is that Kerosene oil was referred to as Krishna Oil, since the English word Kerosene could not be pronounced by the locals, hence, the word got morphed into Krishna oil. The song thus helps in understanding the etymology of a morphed word.

These kinds of texts reflect the literary tradition and the habit of recording mundane things that prevailed among the masses. Failing to preserve these kinds of things would result in the erasure of the literary contribution of the masses.

Next is a small book titled, '*Desiya Oonjal Nalungu - Kadhar and Madhu Vilakku*' published by one E.S. Sivaramalingam Pillai of Ambasamudram. The book consists of songs that encourage people to boycott foreign clothes and buy swadeshi dresses, and also asks them to give up toddy consumption. Above the title, the book starts with a note, '*Gandhi Adigalin Viruppam Niraiveruga*' and features a photo of Mahatma Gandhi on its front page. The book clearly establishes the presence of Gandhian philosophy even in remote villages and by collating it with the history of freedom movement, one can see that many individuals from Tirunelveli district,⁷ where this book was prevalent, were arrested and imprisoned under the 'Prevention of Molestation and Boycotting Ordinance, (Ordinance V of 1932)'.⁸ The ordinance specifically targeted individuals who were involved in toddy shop picketing and the boycott of foreign clothes during the Civil Disobedience Movement of 1932. In this way, a small book safeguards fascinating local narratives of the freedom struggle in the periphery.

Protecting colonial-era jails and erecting monuments to remember the freedom struggle alone does not preserve the heritage of our independence movement but rather preserving texts like these, in addition, preserves the wide heritage of the national movement and also allows us to understand the heritage of the periphery, which need not always be represented by grand monuments or architectural splendour. Digitally documenting these kinds of works, which, in addition to being transmitted as heritage entities, would also be very helpful in folklore and sub-altern studies, and turning them into an OCR-enabled text would also be useful for easier access.

QR Codes on Signboards – as mentioned above, heritage should not be restricted to monuments and grand buildings; even ordinary streets and road names, marginal in historical knowledge, can do that task. One such street and one such road, located in the historic city of Tiruchirappalli, are considered here, and the ways to preserve that are given below.

The street is '*Wandikara Theru*', located in the area known as '*Uraiyur*', the capital city of the Sangam-era Cholas, in Tiruchirappalli. The street contained native household factories, which were popular for making cigars that were famous in European countries. Those cigars were known by the names, '*Trichinopoly Cigar*' or '*Tritchies*' and they were featured in many western movies (Alfred Hitchcock's 1938 movie '*The Lady Vanishes*') and in literature (Sir Arthur Conan Doyle's 1887 Sherlock Holmes novel – '*A Study in Scarlet*'). And the biggest foreign customer for this cigar was none other than the former British Prime Minister, Sir Winston Churchill.⁹ As time passes, all these stories have faded out, and only the street survives.

In a similar manner, this kind of forgetfulness happened to a road which was named after a person who was a native of the city and was also an official of the city, but a peripheral man from the colonial perspective, whereas the roads carrying the names of British collectors and judges were remembered as they have entered into popular memory, and the English names automatically point to the colonial era, which also helps in remembering. This was a privilege that a Tamil name could not secure, as the rest of the road names were also in Tamil and without any significant history, making one particularly significant road name difficult to distinguish from the rest.

And that road is '*Pattabhiraman Salai*', located in the vicinity of Tennur in Tiruchirappalli. The road was named after Rao Bahadur Pattabhiraman Pillai, who, through his hard work, rose to the position of deputy collector of Tiruchirappalli and was also a person with great love and devotion towards the Tamil language.¹⁰ He was a close acquaintance of U.V. Swaminatha Iyer's teacher and constantly urged the scholars of Thiruvaduthurai Adheenam to bring out a good Tamil dictionary.¹¹ Also, he was the one to whom, the Prince of Wales, Albert Edward (later King Edward VII of England), on his visit to Tiruchirappalli in 1875, expressed his admiration for the effects created by the pyrotechnics and lighting over the Rock-fort temple, which had been arranged as a welcome measure.¹² Except for the road name, which itself is just a hollow name with no meaning to the citizens of the district, none of this story survives in the popular memory.

These small, trivial things hold within themselves the stories and memories of people and events, which once played a major role in boosting the economy and the pride of the city of Tiruchirappalli. But without proper documentation, they slowly faded out from popular memory.

To solve this problem and to protect these heritages, digital technology becomes very useful. A simple solution would be pasting QR code stickers or engraving QR codes on the street signboards and the road signboards. Anyone walking across such streets and roads could

easily scan these codes and read, watch videos or listen to audios hosted on a digital platform, which could be updated and which narrates the history of the place. Rather than erecting big hoardings and posters to elaborate the history, using smart technologies like this would be very useful. This kind of information, hosted on the internet, could be accessed anytime, anywhere and by anyone who has an interest in knowing the heritage of the city. In this way, heritage of these mundane objects could be added to the larger fold, along with big buildings and forts.

Conclusion

It has been established by various scholars and academicians that history and culture do not belong only to the core. The memories of the periphery should equally be respected and preserved. Only if that has been done do those things enter into the pages of history. And only after that do they become heritage that can be imparted to future generations. Digital technologies are very useful in taking a step in that direction, as suggested above. By doing so, the spectrum of heritage would grow, which in turn would bring greater pride to any society. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the historians and academicians to carry this task forward.

References

-
- ¹ Guha, Ranajit. *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India*. Oxford: Oxford University Press., 1983.
 - ² Spivak, Gayatri Chakravorty. "Can the Subaltern Speak?" in *Marxism and the Interpretation of Culture*, edited by Cary Nelson and Lawrence Grossberg. Urbana: University of Illinois Press., 1988.
 - ³ Kundera, Milan. *The Book of Laughter and Forgetting*. translated by Aaron Asher. London: Faber and Faber., 1996, p.2.
 - ⁴ Venkatachalapathy, A.R. *Muchandi Ilakkiyam*, Nagercoil: Kalachuvadu Publications., 2023.
 - ⁵ Krishnan, Pramila. "Gujili Ilakkiyathai Meetteduka Kalamirangiya Chennai Pengal". BBC Tamil. (14 September 2018): <https://www.bbc.com/tamil/arts-and-culture-45500396>
 - ⁶ Venkatachalapathy, op. cit., p.151.
 - ⁷ Somayajulu, S.N. *Nellai Mavatta Suthanthira Poratta Varalaru*. Tirunelveli: Hilal Press., 1976
 - ⁸ Government of Tamil Nadu. *Who's who of Freedom Fighters (Tamil Nadu): Volume Three*. Madras: Director of Stationery and Printing., 1973.
 - ⁹ Micheal Nithyn, Maria. "Trichinopoly to Ten Downing Street: 'Tritchies' and the cigar capitalism" in *Proceedings of the South Indian History Congress 42.*, 2024. https://journal.southindianhistorycongress.org/show_article.php?atl_id=NjMx
 - ¹⁰ Iyer, Swaminatha. *En Sarithiram*. Chennai: Natrinai Pathipagam., 2022, p.392.
 - ¹¹ Ibid., p.393.
 - ¹² Russell, William Howard. *The Prince of Wales Tour – A Diary in India*. Second edition. London: Sampson Low, Marston, Searle and Rivington., 1877., p.314.